

A STORY OF FEARLESS WAR JOURNALIST: THE LIFE AND LEGACY OF RAHIMULLAH YOUSAFZAI

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Abstract

This article explores the life, career, and enduring legacy of Rahimullah Yousafzai, one of Pakistan's most distinguished journalists and analysts. The primary objectives are to examine his biography and personality, trace his educational and professional milestones, assess his contributions to journalism and society, and evaluate the national and international recognition he received. The study is guided by research questions focusing on the formative influences in Yousafzai's early life, the personal traits that shaped his journalistic approach, his impact on public discourse concerning Afghanistan and Pakistan, the defining elements of his legacy, and the honors bestowed upon him. A qualitative research methodology was adopted, utilizing in-depth interviews and focus group discussions to gather comprehensive insights. The research population comprised individuals closely associated with Rahimullah Yousafzai, including family members, friends, and professional colleagues from Mardan, Peshawar, and surrounding regions. Purposive sampling ensured the selection of participants who could provide rich, relevant data about his life and work. Data collection involved twenty open-ended questions administered through interviews at varied locations, such as his home, workplace, and other significant sites. Two focus group discussions were also conducted: one with colleagues at The News International Peshawar and another with former internees mentored by Yousafzai. Findings reveal that Rahimullah Yousafzai was celebrated for his professionalism, humility, and fearless reporting, particularly his rare interviews with figures such as Osama bin Laden and Mullah Muhammad Omar. He was a mentor to many, a mediator in regional conflicts, and a tireless advocate for the marginalized, especially the people of FATA. His contributions to journalism were recognized through prestigious awards, including the Tamgha-i-Imtiaz and Sitara-i-Imtiaz. The study concludes that Yousafzai's ethical standards, commitment to public service, and role in shaping war journalism and media ethics in Pakistan have left an indelible mark, inspiring future generations of journalists and enhancing the international profile of Pakistani journalism.

INTRODUCTION

Rahimullah Yousafzai was one of Pakistan's most renowned journalists and analysts. Widely respected for his political insight, social commentary, and expertise in national security affairs, Rahimullah Yousafzai gained international recognition for his rare interviews with Osama bin Laden and Taliban leader Mullah Muhammad Omar. He was born on September 10, 1954, in Shamoza village, located in the Mardan district of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. He received his early education in his village before moving to Peshawar and Jhelum for further schooling. Later, he studied at DJ Sindh Science College and the University of Karachi (Usman, 2021).

Personal Life and Personality

Yousafzai came from a humble background. One of eight siblings, he often proudly mentioned that his father was a soldier who was imprisoned during the 1971 war. After moving to Karachi, Rahimullah Yousafzai worked nights as a watchman while attending college during the day. Despite financial hardships, he remained committed to education and journalism. He would write on his typewriter under candlelight, sitting on rooftops due to power outages. His life was a story of resilience and determination. Known for his humility, Rahimullah Yousafzai always treated rich and poor alike and avoided raising his voice. Even in anger, he would calmly say, "How strange you are." He deeply valued the Pashto

language and refused high-profile government positions, such as a ministry offered by General Pervez Musharraf, choosing instead to remain a journalist. He believed the media should serve the people by solving real problems rather than amplifying political rhetoric (Yusufzai, 2021).

Career and Achievements

Rahimullah Yousafzai was not only a journalist but a historian of his time. He began reporting during the Soviet-Afghan war in 1979 and became a leading expert on Taliban movements, Afghan politics, and Pakistan's tribal belt. His career began as a proofreader in Karachi and evolved into key roles at national and international media organizations. He was the resident editor of *The News International* in Peshawar, a correspondent for *Time Magazine*, and a long-time contributor to BBC Radio.

His fearless reporting led him to interview Osama bin Laden twice and Taliban leader Mullah Omar multiple times both at a time when access to them was nearly impossible. His extensive travels to conflict zones, including Kandahar, Kabul, and Pakistan's tribal areas, added unmatched depth to his journalism. Despite opportunities abroad and offers from the government, Rahimullah Yousafzai remained rooted in ethical, people-centered reporting (Alvi & Ali, 2021).

Fig. 12: Ibrahim Haqqani being interviewed by Rahimullah Yousafzai and Lynn Doucet after the capture of Khost in 1991 (Source: Robert Nickleberg)

Taliban officials foreign journalists, including Rahimullah Yousafzai (C, kneeling) of the BBC's Pashto-language service, examine an unexploded U.S. bomb November 1, 2001 in a deserted area in Chokar Karez, Afghanistan, about 80 kms north of Kandahar. (Photo by Robert Nickelsberg/Getty Images).

Services to Journalism

To understand Rahimullah Yousafzai impact, it's important to define journalism itself. According to the Merriam-Webster Dictionary, journalism is "the collection and editing of news for presentation through the media." For Rahimullah Yousafzai, journalism wasn't just a profession it was a mission.

He inherited a sense of public service from his father and became a lifeline for the people of Mardan and beyond. He never saw journalism as a job but as a responsibility to serve the public. Even while seriously ill, he continued to write and inspire. His unpublished book, written during his final days, remains a symbol of his commitment.

He mentored many young journalists, trained them, and treated them as family. He was always approachable, never declined a call, and remained calm and composed with everyone, regardless of their status (Kakakhel, 2021).

Contributions to Society

According to Hassan Khan, a senior journalist and director at AVT Channels, Rahimullah Yousafzai wasn't just a journalist—he was a benefactor. He

helped hundreds of poor individuals secure jobs and solve social issues in his community. He never misused his influence and stayed grounded in simplicity.

He was the only journalist who presented the issues of Afghanistan and FATA (Federally Administered Tribal Areas) at the international level in an unbiased and accurate manner. His ability to write obituaries and report sensitively on death and

tragedy was unmatched. Rahimullah Yousafzai was not just respected—he was loved and trusted (Khan, 2021).

Awards and Recognition

In recognition of his exceptional services to journalism, the Government of Pakistan awarded Rahimullah Yousafzai the Tamgha-i-Imtiaz in 2005

and the Sitara-i-Imtiaz in 2010. These prestigious honors reflect his credibility, courage, and impact on national and international journalism (Dawn, 2021).

Death and Legacy

Rahimullah Yousafzai passed away on September 9, 2021, after battling cancer for over 15 months. His funeral was held in his native village of Shamozai, Mardan, and was attended by notable figures, including Prime Minister Imran Khan, Army Chief General Qamar Javed Bajwa, and leaders of various political parties.

Imran Khan tweeted: “Saddened to learn of Rahimullah Yusufzai’s passing. He was one of Pakistan’s most respected journalists and an opinion maker.” His son, Arshad Yusufzai, himself a journalist, confirmed his death and acknowledged the tremendous legacy his father left behind (Khairi, 2021).

Respect within country

The BBC reporter Matt Frei used to tell the story – true, I have no doubt – that he was once travelling on a Pakistan Airlines domestic flight with Rahimullah Yusufzai, Pakistan's best-known journalist. Anxious because his friend was late, Frei asked the check-in desk if they could hold the plane for a few minutes. "Sir," the check-in clerk replied. "This plane will not take off unless Rahimullah Yusufzai is on board." Now that is what you call respect.

Respect within Taliban

I suspect Yusufzai is admired as much by the Afghan Taliban leadership as he is by Pakistani politicians. "The Taliban respect me because I was the first journalist to visit Kandahar when the Taliban emerged. I was the first journalist to meet Mullah Omar in March of 1995. I gave the first detailed account of the Taliban. They said to me later, 'You introduced us to the world'.

Research Objectives:

To explore the biography and personality of Rahimullah Yusufzai

To identify his educational background and career milestones

To examine his services, contributions, and societal impacts

To assess national and international recognition received

Research Questions:

What shaped Rahimullah Yusufzai's early life and education?

What unique personality traits influenced his journalism?

How did his reporting influence public discourse on Afghanistan and Pakistan?

Which contributions define his legacy?

What recognition and awards did he receive?

Literature Review

Rahimullah Yousafzai, a legendary figure in Pakistani journalism, was born on September 10, 1954, in Shamoza village near Katlang, District Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. His early education began in his hometown before he moved to Jhelum, where his

father was serving in the Pakistan Army. He enrolled in the Army Academy in Jhelum, reflecting his family's hope that he would pursue a military career. However, fate had other plans, and his path diverged toward journalism.

Known for his intelligence, tall stature, and active participation in academics and extracurricular activities, Rahimullah Yousafzai gained several awards during his early school life. His stage presence and oratory skills were remarkable. Later, he moved to Karachi to continue his studies while also working part-time to support his family. He was accepted into DJ Sindh Science College and subsequently enrolled at the University of Karachi (Alvi & Yusuf, 2021).

Rahimullah Yousafzai journalism career began in Karachi, where he contributed to several national magazines. His credibility and recognition rose sharply after he conducted exclusive interviews with Osama bin Laden and Taliban leader Mullah Muhammad Omar. His reporting provided rare access and nuanced understanding of Afghan affairs, making him one of the most respected war correspondents in South Asia. He served as the editor of *The News International* and contributed to international media outlets such as BBC Urdu, BBC Pashto, and *Time Magazine*.

His coverage of the Afghan conflict dates back to the Soviet invasion in 1979, continuing through the Taliban's rise in the 1990s. In 1995, he traveled to Kandahar and other conflict zones, reporting from areas few journalists dared to enter. For his fearless and impactful journalism, he was awarded the *Tamgha-e-Imtiaz* in 2004 and *Sitara-e-Imtiaz* in 2009 by the Government of Pakistan (Khan, 2021; Waheed, 2021).

Despite humble beginnings, Rahimullah Yousafzai dedication was unwavering. He once worked as a janitor in Karachi for just 100 rupees a month while pursuing his education. These experiences shaped his worldview and embedded strong ethical foundations in his journalism. He became globally known after his interviews with Osama bin Laden were aired worldwide in 1995 (Azad, 2021).

He never aligned with political parties and upheld neutrality in all his reporting. His colleagues described him as punctual, humble, and deeply committed. Nasreen (2021) recalls him as a man of immense kindness who always spoke with humility

despite his towering presence in journalism. Professionally, Rahimullah Yousafzai was the first to reach the office and the last to leave. He often spent late nights typing stories, sometimes falling asleep at his desk. He trained and mentored many young journalists, instilling in them values of integrity and perseverance (Rahimullah Yousafzai, 2021).

He also highlighted critical media issues in his analyses, including the impact of propaganda, the role of foreign broadcasters like BBC and VOA, and the importance of media literacy. He advocated for purposeful local journalism to counter disinformation in remote areas (Ur Rahman et al.). According to Siddique (2011), Rahimullah Yousafzai played a pivotal role in training both national and international journalists in conflict reporting. His ethical standards aligned with guidelines set by SAFMA and the Federal Union of Journalists in Pakistan (Niaz, Adnan & Irtiza, 2020). Even in his final months battling cancer, he remained engaged in journalism. His last interview, given to journalist Tariq Saeed, unveiled lesser-known aspects of his life and career. His funeral, held on September 9, 2021, in Katlang, drew thousands, including senior journalists and political leaders (Tribune, 2021). Rahimullah Yousafzai unparalleled access to Osama bin Laden and Mullah Omar and his role as a mentor and policy analyst remain unmatched in South Asian journalism. As Wilner (2010) and Jones (2010) assert, Rahimullah Yousafzai presence in the international media landscape symbolized integrity, courage, and dedication to truth.

Research Methodology

Research methodology provides the conceptual framework for conducting research. It is a systematic and logical scheme that reflects the researcher's philosophical stance and informs the choice of methods and procedures used to address research questions. This study employs a qualitative research methodology with In-depth interviews and focus group discussion designs to explore the life, career, and contributions of veteran journalist Rahimullah Yousafzai. Data was gathered through in-depth interviews with his family members, colleagues, and friends.

Qualitative research involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data to understand concepts,

opinions, or experiences. It is commonly used in fields such as media studies, sociology, anthropology, and education. In this study, qualitative research was used to collect data through interviews, observations, and focus group discussions. This approach helps uncover deeper meanings and provides rich insights into the subject's life and legacy.

In-depth Interview

In-depth interviews were conducted with ten individuals, including Rahimullah Yousafzai family, friends, and colleagues. The researcher used open-ended questions to allow participants to share their narratives freely. These discussions provided nuanced insights into his personal values, journalistic ethics, and societal contributions.

Focus Group Discussion

The researcher conducted focus group discussion with two different groups including Rahim ullah Yusufzai colleagues, and internees, In The News international. A focus group discussion (FGD) is a qualitative research technique that brings together individuals with shared characteristics or interests to discuss specific topics in a moderated environment. It is designed to gather rich, detailed data based on shared experiences and perspectives. According to George (2021), FGDs are particularly useful for exploring perceptions, behaviors, and attitudes in an open and interactive setting. Nyumba et al. (2018) further emphasize that FGDs enable participants to agree or disagree naturally, revealing the breadth and depth of their opinions. This makes FGDs an effective tool in media and social research for capturing context-rich data.

Population and Sampling

The population for this study consists of individuals who had a close association with Rahimullah Yusufzai. This includes his family members, friends, and professional colleagues based in Mardan, Peshawar, and surrounding areas. Purposive sampling was applied to ensure that the data collected would be rich and relevant. Individuals who had professional or personal relationships with Rahimullah Yousafzai were chosen based on their ability to provide valuable information about his life and work.

Data Collection & Analysis

The researcher collected data using a set of 20 open-ended questions. Interviews were scheduled and conducted with the selected individuals at different locations including Rahimullah Yousafzai home, his workplace, and other sites in Peshawar, Mardan, and Katlung.

Results and Discussion

The researcher conducted two focus group discussions to gain deeper insights into the life, personality, and journalistic legacy of veteran journalist Rahimullah Yousafzai. The participants included his colleagues at The News International Peshawar and a group of former internees who had worked under his mentorship.

Focus group discussion with colleagues:

In this case, the researcher, took time from the Rahim ullah Yusufzai colleagues to discuss his personality, career, services and awards. The researcher visited to The News International Peshawar bureau office in this regard. Four of his colleagues were agreed to take participant in the discussion.

Responding to the question, They said that, he was a great person and a good boss. He would not object to a demand by an employee for leave. He was also humble person. In addition, he used to encourage young and junior colleagues in the office. Therefore, it has been found that he was a kind person.

To other quarry, they also stated that Rahim ullah Yusufzai was a hardworking person, this is why he made his name as a journalist. He also had good contacts in various spheres. It shows his devotion and patience for his work. To other quarry, they explore that in fact, his English language was good since his young age because of his good schooling. So language never come as a barrier his the way of his journalistic work.

They also added that, he was a good reader and a very good writer too. An appreciable aspect of his life was that he was a hardworking journalist. This shows his love for reading books and writing creatively. They also said that, he got several awards, acknowledging his achievement in

the filed of journalism. He was decorated with the medal of distinction (Tamgha-E- Imtiaz) in 2005 and then he received (Sitara-E- Imtiaz) from the president of Pakistan in 2010. He also received pride of performance award. He won several awards from journalist union and organization's. This was a clear sign for his perfection in his works.

To another quarry they explored that, his interviewed with Osama bin laden and Afghan leader mullah Omar made him much popular journalist. He also knew the leader of Afghan Taliban as compare to other. He was also popular for writing obituaries on famous people on their death. such interviews reflect his contacts in every sphere of life with any types of people. They added that, he not only became popular himself but also, he made the Khyber pukhtunkhwa province known for people in other countries. Because of his good journalism practices. He shows that poor background never turned as a hurdle in achieving his goals. To a quarry they stated that, Yusufzai was among the first journalists to report on the Taliban. He was one of the few bona fide experts on Afghanistan. He had sources in Afghan Taliban, this is why, his stories of Afghanistan were considered trustworthy.

They added that, he was a good observer and reader because of this he considered an active journalist. They further said that, he write on issues of Khyber pukhtunkhwa. Often he would wrote obituaries on famous people on their death. They explored that, he promoted international journalism through local and national media. Secondly he give expert opinion with balance and neutral way to insure subjectivity. and also they revealed that, he attended various journalism training and also trained several journalists in country.

They said that, due to authentic information and good relations with pak- Afghan influencers he was respectable for Pakistan, Afghanistan and pressure groups both sides. Most of the time both government made him a mediator for dialogue. In responding to a question "which segment of society followed him?" they explored that' elderly people used to listen his

commentary on BBC. Afghani would also listen his news analysis. Also, government authorities in Khyber pukhtunkhwa take note of his writing and his stories, directions for solution of the issues. They stated that he also highlighted the issues of ex-FATA through his writings. He raised awareness among people about FATA problems and other matters. Yusufzai was considered an authority on Afghan affairs and on the federally administered tribal area FATA of Pakistan.

4.3 Focus group discussion with internees:

They added that, being a journalist he was very down to earth and simple man. They also said that he was very good person and help the poor and needy people of the society. He used his influence not for his cast and family but, used for the social development of our area, finding jobs for hundreds of poor people and solving their problems was one of the goal of his life. Therefore, he was a humble personality and gentleman.

They said that, he was a political and security analyst and expert on the north western tribal region of the Taliban so, he was much famous due to the commands on Afghan affairs. Further they added that he was a good journalist. Respondents explore that, the appreciable aspect of his life was that he was not only a hard worker but also social worker. He was a devoted worker. He did not hesitate to go to the most dangerous places related to his journalists responsibilities and submit a wonderful stories. He would do journalism to serve our people and help them and bring their problems forward. He was a very hardworking man and his whole life was journalism.

They stated that, the government of Pakistan first awarded him Tamgha-E- Imtiaz award in 2005. And then he received Sitara-E- Imtiaz award from the president of Pakistan for his achievement in the filed of journalism on 23, March, 2010. Respondent said that, the most admirable work of his career was mediation between Tahrek Taliban and Pakistan.

They explore that, he attended journalism trainings and he trained many journalists in his career. He supported and encouraged youngsters.

Respondent said that, Peshawar based journalist were consider expert in the country tribal regions of Afghanistan and the Taliban. He met and interviewed with Osama bin laden twice and Afghan Taliban leader mullah Muhamad Omar during his trip.

They added that, his work on Afghan Taliban is much commendable because, he worked during war in Afghanistan. They also said that, he reported the ground realities of Afghanistan during war in terror. Respondents stated that keeping concentration on journalists affairs made him an active journalist. He also said that due to his love and hardworking in journalism made him an active journalist.

They said that, he trained local journalists and polish their skills. He also said that a number of local journalists learned from him. As he was a role model. Respondents explore that, he was a role model for local journalists, he encouraged the young journalists.

What are the impact of his work on pak - Afghan relation? Respondents said that the impact of his work on pak-Afghan relation was mediation between Pakistan and Afghanistan. They said that, all journalists society followed his segment, and also stated all segment of society followed him. Respondents said that, he aware all the people of former FATA. And further explain, he always raised voice for former FATA people rights. He was the only person to explore Afghanistan and FATA. Ex- FATA and Afghanistan news value credit goes to Yusufzai because, he presented it in a good way.

4.4 Interviewed with his son:

Where did he get his education?

He get his education in Military college jehlum, Mardan college and DJ sindh government science college.

When he stated job?

He started odds job in 1974.

When he started his formal journalism, and which organizations' he joined?

He started his career at The sun in 1978.

Which are the unique feature of his life?

His truthfulness, easy approachable, time for anyone wishing to meet and respect to all, helping

the poor and needy in any possible way, he was a social worker and also a hard worker etc.

Why is he so much famous?

For presenting true stories without taking side, uncovering real facts, meeting with Osama bin Laden twice, and Taliban founding commander Mullah Muhammad Omar a dozen times.

Why he was attracted to write English newspapers instead of Urdu?

He was attracted to write English newspapers instead of Urdu because he wanted to reach maximum number of audience at national and international level.

Which aspect of his life are appreciable?

His honesty, truthfulness, hardworking, helping the poor and resolving the problems of community and general public are the appreciable aspect of his life.

Which awards he got in his career?

He got Tamgha-e-Imtiaz, Sitara-e-Imtiaz and among others.

What is the most admirable work of his career?

The most admirable work of his career interviewed Osama bin Laden twice when no one can access to the world most wanted man

He is credited in introducing the Afghan Taliban to the world by introducing their foundation leader Mullah Muhammad Omar for BBC Pushto radio service.

What are the prominent outcomes of his journalistic work?

That a journalist should not be party to any news story. Keeping in view the safety aspect of working in the field, he often tell young journalist that no story is more important than journalist safety.

A journalist should always listen to the person sharing the news and take views of acquirer, the acquired and independent individuals or source who is aware of the matter.

When and whom he met during his Afghan trip?

He met all the top politicians, warlords, Mujahedeen, Taliban commanders and Al-Qaeda leadership during his dozen of his visit to Afghanistan since the start of Soviet invasion.

Why his work on Afghan Taliban is much commendable?

He had unlimited and unhindered access to Afghan Taliban leadership across the country. He was able to acquire first-hand information from on ground

sources. The Taliban respected him a lot for his unbiased journalism.

Which thing made him an active journalist?

Identifying and highlighting issues of his region.

What are the benefits of his services to local journalism?

He was an inspiration of hundreds of youngest in journalism. He introducing covering war journalism in Pakistan.

Which new ideas and thoughts of his work for local journalism?

Covering war journalism covering the effected people of the war either civilian or military personnel.

What are the impact of his work for local journalism?

Hundreds of young students adopted the field of journalism as their profession.

What are the impact of his work on Pak - Afghan relation?

His analysis paved the way for peace between the two countries.

Which segment of society followed him?

Every segment of society followed him.

What are the contribution for the development of former FATA?

Presentation the issues of FATA region highlighted the miseries of tribesmen and henceforth development work to some extent started to improve the life standard of their.

Conclusion:

It is concluded that Peshawar base journalist Rahim Ullah Yusufzai was among the first journalist to report the Taliban. He was one of the few expert on Afghanistan. He also interviewed twice with Osama bin Laden and Afghan Taliban leader Mullah Muhammad Umar. His work on Afghan Taliban is much commendable because, he worked during war in Afghanistan. He reported the ground realities of Afghanistan during war in terror. He met all the top politicians, warlords, Mujahedeen, Taliban commanders and Al-Qaeda leadership during his dozen of his visit to Afghanistan since the start of Soviet invasion.

It is also summarized that because have expertise on Pak-Afghan relations he was respectable to all parties in both countries. Most of the time both

government made him mediator in dialogues. He was also a mediation between Tahrek Taliban and Pakistan. He interviewed twice with Osama bin Laden twice when no one can access to the world wanted man.

He also highlighted the issues of former FATA through his writing. He aware all the people of former FATA and raised voice for them. He was the only person to explore Afghanistan and former FATA. Yusufzai was considered an authority on Afghan affairs and on the federally administered tribal area of FATA of Pakistan. Afghanistan and FATA news value credit goes to Yusufzai because, he presented it in a good way. He presented the issues of FATA region and highlighted the miseries of tribesmen and henceforth development work to some extent started to improve the life standard of their.

It is known that he was a humble hardworking person. He was a good reader and a good writer too. He was also popular for writing obituaries on famous people on their death. He loved to reading books and writing creatively. Being a journalist he was very down and simple man. He help the poor and needy people of the society. He was not only a hard worker but also a social worker he solved hundreds of people problems was one of the goal of his life. He made the Khyber pukhtunkhwa province known for people in other countries. His honesty, truthfulness, hardworking, helping the poor and resolving the problem of community and general public are the appreciable aspect of his life.

It is found that he was a great and a good boss. He used to encourage young and junior journalist. He was a good observer and reader because of this he considered an active journalist. He used his influence not for his family but, used for the social development of our society. He was a devoted worker. He would do journalism to serve our people and help them and bring their problems forward.

It is gathered that he trained local journalists and polish their skills, hundreds of local learn from him. He was a role model for local journalists. He attended various journalism and training and also trained several journalists in

country. He promoted international journalism through local and national media.

It is decided that he got several awards, acknowledging his achievement in the filed of journalism. Government of Pakistan first awarded him medal of distinction (Tamgha -E-Imtiaz) in 2005. And then he received (Sitara-E-Imtiaz) from the president of Pakistan in 2010. He also received pride of performance award. He won several awards from journalist union and organizations.

Recommendations for Future Research:

Comparative studies between Rahimullah Yousafzai reporting style and other global conflict journalists. Studies focusing on his impact on public perception regarding Taliban and Afghan conflicts.

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